

CDA NEWSLETTER

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BAYERO UNIVERSITY
KANO

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DRYLAND AGRICULTURE**
AN AFRICA CENTRE OF EXCELLENCE

CENTRE FOR DRYLAND AGRICULTURE

Bayero University, Kano – Nigeria

... an Africa Centre of Excellence

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Resilient and Prosperous African Drylands

MISSION

To improve livelihood, resilience and sustainable use of natural resources in African drylands through training and demand-driven research

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- Passion and Teamwork
- Commitment and Sacrifice
- Integrity and Transparency
- Professionalism and Excellence

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Sorting seeds for datepalm mother plants

CDA Research Raises Hope of Commercial Production of Date-Palm in Nigeria

CDA's research work on sex identification at seedlings stage has raised hope for commercial date palm production in Nigeria with farmers expressing confidence that it would soon become an exporter of this nutritious product, thereby boosting the country's Gross Domestic Product (GDP).

Date palm is a dioecious crop with separate male and female plants. It is often difficult to identify the fruit bearing female plants at seedling stage until after 5 years of cultivation.

While responding to a request by the Professional Farmers Association of Kano and Jigawa states, the Centre for Dryland Agriculture (CDA) set up a research

team to develop molecular tools for sex identification in date palm.

Specific molecular markers have been developed to identify the sex of date palm seedlings at three leaf stage. This has raised the hope for commercial production of the date palm in the country.

Farmers have heaved a sigh of relief that subsistence farming would soon pave the way for commercial production, especially in Jigawa state and some other parts of the country where there is competitive advantage to cultivate date palm.

During an interaction with farmers, community leaders and traditional rulers held at the Dutse Emirate Council in Jigawa State recently, the Centre for Dryland Agriculture (CDA) expatiated more on how the research discovery came into fruition as a result of several laboratory tests and analysis at Molecular Biology Laboratory and Tissue Culture Laboratory, one of the best of their kind in West and Central Africa.

The Deputy Director Research, Dr. Kabir Mustapha Umar, who led the delegation, said CDA would continue to partner with farmers and community leaders to address some of the challenges facing them with a view to contributing optimally in terms of boosting food security. He said the centre had been receiving tremendous support from the Vice Chancellor, Professor Sagir Adamu Abbas.

According to Dr Sani Lawan, one of the scientists in in the project "Farming of datepalm in Nigeria is at subsistence level". He noted that farming at

commercial level was possible, since Jigawa State was naturally endowed.

He added that Nigeria imports 67,880 tons of datepalm every year which costs about N170 billion, noting that if the production was done in Nigeria and the money got into the hands of our farmers, it would significantly boost income generation and improve farming datepalm in the country

The Emir of Dutse, who was represented by the District Head of Balagu, Alhaji Shehu Datti, said farmers of datepalm in Nigeria were excited when the information was disseminated to them. Jigawa State being the hub of datepalm production would maximally utilize the opportunity in order to boost its farming, thereby becoming a net exporter. He thanked Bayero University and the CDA Team, saying that the seedlings would be distributed across all the agricultural zones in the state as directed by the Governor.

Also speaking, the Head of Afforestation in Dutse, Inuwa Ahmad Baffa, and Rabiuh Shehu of Gundumar Hakimin Dutse both expressed happiness over the new research discovery. They said it had solved the myriad challenges faced by farmers of datepalm across the country.

Observation of tissue cultured plantlets

Nursery of datepalm seedlings in Screen House

The Centre for Dry land Agriculture expatiated more on how the research discovery came into fruition as a result of several laboratory tests and analysis at Molecular Biology Laboratory and Tissue Culture Laboratory, one of the best of their kind in West and Central Africa

Nursery of datepalm seedlings inspection in Screen House

Deputy Director, Research of CDA, Dr Kabir Mustapha Umar explaining the discovery of sex identified date-palm seedlings to the traditional rulers of Dutse Emirate in Jigawa State

A group photograph of the CDA Team, farmers and traditional rulers of Dutse Emirate in Jigawa State

CDA Conducts Workshop on Establishing Strategic Partnership

Centre for Dryland Agriculture (CDA) has conducted a training workshop on Establishing Strategic Partnership under the Initiatives for Sustainable Food Security in Dryland (ISPOSID) project.

The objective of the training was to train and build capacity of academics and researchers from Bayero University, Kano and other tertiary institutions towards engagement with private and public sectors.

About 60 participants from Bayero University, Kano, Federal College of Education (FCE), Kano, Federal College of Education (FCET) Bichi, Kano State Polytechnic, Sa'adatu Rimi College of Education, as well as College of Arts and Science (CAS) attended the workshop.

Others were from Kano University of Science and Technology and Federal College of Agricultural Produce Technology, Kano.

Director CDA, Prof. Jibrin M. Jibrin

Modules of the training workshop were Partnership Building to Effectively Implement Research and Development Project and Participatory Research and Extension Approach for Sustainable Agricultural Development. The training took place at the ICRISAT Kano office.

Stakeholders brainstorming on establishing strategic partnership

STAKEHOLDERS PROVIDE INPUT FOR ESTABLISHING CDA AGRIC-BUSINESS INNOVATION HUB

Stakeholders from diverse technology and innovation hubs have brainstormed and provided credible and incisive input on how best to establish and run the Centre for Dryland Agriculture's Innovation Accelerator Hub.

To achieve this, CDA organized a one-day inclusive stakeholder workshop in which key stakeholders met and discussed extensively. Key suggestions and input were provided during the workshop.

Participants of the training were drawn from various innovation hubs in the country that included Technology Incubation Centre, Vertical Farms Venture

Limited, Blue Sapphire Limited and Shamrock Innovation Hub.

Others were Digital Development Hub, Innovate Lab, Start Bench Hub and ICRI SAT.

Participants brainstormed and provided input and ideas on how best to establish and effectively run the CDA's innovation hub.

The CDA Agric-Innovation hub will be a skills development centre for Agribusiness entrepreneurs. It will also provide a working space for Agribusiness Startups and Agribusiness companies that need a place to grow their businesses.

A group photograph of the participants of the workshop

CDA's Short Term Trainees Establish Business Enterprises, Provide Employment Opportunities

The Centre for Dryland Agriculture (CDA), Bayero University, Kano has trained over 2,000 professionals through short-term courses with a view to impacting the necessary skills and requisite knowledge in line with one of the Centre's mandates of training skilled manpower to address some of Africa's developmental challenges.

One of the trainings conducted was a need-based training by Kano, Kaduna and Kogi States under the World Bank funded "Agro-Processing Productivity Enhancement and Livelihood Improvement Support Project (APPEALS)", where the Centre was engaged to train 1400 women and youth in rice, poultry and aquaculture value chains. The Centre recently conducted a tracer study focusing on the trainees from the APPEALS project. It was discovered that many of the graduate trainees had received their grants and established successful business enterprises in the various agricultural value chains of rice, aquaculture, and fisheries.

Mrs Christopher Mercy, who established an Organic Poultry Production Firm, "Precious Farms and Agricultural Product Ventures" in Kogi State was full of praises to the CDA for imparting knowledge and skills to her that have gone a long way in assisting her to become entrepreneurial.

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CDA Trainee, Merry Christopher providing training to her students on organic poultry farming in Kogi State

CDA Communication Officer, Nura Garba (right) interacting with one of CDA Trainees, who established fish farming in Kaduna State

A CDA trainee feeding her birds

One of CDA trainees is currently operating rice marketing in Kogi State

A CDA Trainee, Samuel Ochima established poultry farming and generates N1.7m monthly

CDA Training Helps Me Generate N1.7 Million Monthly – Samuel Ochima

Ochima, who established a poultry farm called V-Tech Integrated Farms, recalled how he was trained in organic poultry farm at the CDA in which he learned various skills and knowledge that exposed him to modern methods of poultry farming. He said after the training, he went back to his state, Kogi, to establish his small scale business.

Even after the establishment of the business, he still consulted the facilitators of the training for further guidance.

He stated that currently, the business had flourished and he employed the services of men and women to help the business grow and also create employment opportunities for them.

As at the time of conducting this interview, Ochima confirmed that he had generated over N1,750,000 monthly for the sales of eggs and the money kept counting because he was expanding the business. He said only God would reward the CDA because of the knowledge and skills impacted on him.

Mr Samuel Ochimana further said he had employed 5 staff till date.

Ochima confirmed that he generated over N1,750,000 monthly for the sales of eggs and the money keeps counting because he was expanding the business

Our Businesses Become Source of Livelihood – CDA Women Trainees say

One of the successful CDA trainees, Mrs Maryam Bello, whose “Jemtrade Worldwide Aquaculture” enterprises has been established, said the business has become her source of livelihood and that she doesn't need a government job any more. With the knowledge acquired, she was able to develop her small farm where she channels the waste fish water into her farm to grow vegetables.

A group of women in Zaria town of Kaduna State have established an Aquaculture Production enterprise utilizing the CDA training on the business, which has become successful. The women have been producing and selling fish with substantial revenue. Their plan now is to expand the business into processing to generate more revenue.

Mrs Fatima Ahmed Tijjani has ventured into rice marketing in Lokoja, Kogi State. She employed her husband to assist her in selling the rice, which she packages in her small shop. Her business is growing in leaps and bounds using the training acquired from the CDA.

A group of two, Rafat Ahmed Onize and Abideh Ojima Emmanuel said they were inspired by the CDA training to generate huge revenue in their aquaculture business. According to them, they have “implemented the business strategy techniques in the business that's why they have distinguished themselves from others who have not undergone such training”.

Similarly, CDA graduate trainees in Kano who established business enterprises are reaping the benefits of the training. Many of the successful ones have been positively impacting into the economy of the state through providing quality and affordable products and employing women and youth.

No doubt, with the impact made on youth and women across various states of the federation, CDA's mandate of providing skilled manpower to address the challenges of food insufficiency has started yielding a positive impact.

Mrs Maryam Bello, one of CDA trainees who established Jemtrade Worldwide Aquaculture Enterprises

Fatima Ahmed Tijjani, one of CDA trainees

Rafat Ahmed Onize talks about her business enterprises with her partner Abideh Ojima Emmanuel

CDA, WACWISA and ICRISAT Conduct Workshop on Watershed Management

Centre for Dryland Agriculture (CDA), West Africa Centre of Excellence for Water, Irrigation and Sustainable Agriculture of University of Development Studies, Tamale Ghana and International Crops Research Institute for the Semi-Arid Tropics (ICRISAT) organized a one-week training workshop on Integrated Watershed Management for Sustainable Agriculture. The workshop took place in Kano.

The participants of the training were agricultural extension workers, academics, researchers, Postgraduate students, staff from Hadejia Jama'are River Development Authority, HJRBDA and NEWMAP, among others.

The Managing Director of the HJRBDA said the training workshop was timely in view of the challenging climatic conditions, which led to flooding ravaging many parts of Nigeria. He said with the calibre of the facilitators, it would mitigate those challenges and provide a leeway to effectively manage a watershed for sustainable development by the participants.

The Managing Director expressed the hope that CDA has state-of-the-art facilities and competent staff to collaborate with WACWISA to achieve the objectives of the training workshop.

The Dean, School of Engineering and Academic Support Programme and Coordinator of WACWISA, Professor Abdulganiy Shuaib, said WACWISA was established in 2019 by the University of Development Studies (UDS), Ghana as a semi-autonomous Centre of Excellence to undertake cutting-edge research and training in irrigation, drainage, water resources management, sustainable agriculture, climate change and food and nutrition security.

He said, CDA and WACWISA in collaboration with other research centres could play a critical role in addressing the perennial challenges of food insecurity in Africa. He added that the two centres would explore more collaborative opportunities in research, staff and student exchange.

Earlier in his welcome remarks, the Director of CDA, Professor Jibrin Mohammed Jibrin, welcomed the WACWISA team to Kano and indeed Nigeria. He stated that collaboration between the two centres kick-started at the 7th ACEs meeting held in Cotonou, Benin Republic in June 2022.

The modules of the workshop centered on Introduction to Watershed Hydrology and Management; Integrated Watershed Management;

A view of the WACWISA Training Workshop on Watershed Management in Kano

Director CDA, Prof Jibrin M. Jibrin (left) presenting a CDA customized T-Shirt to one of the participants of the workshop

Improving Climate Resilience through Integrated Watershed Management and Watershed Management and Water Harvesting for Sustainable Agriculture and Groundwater Recharge.

Others were Improving Climate Change on Watershed Hydrology and Impact of Climate Change on Watershed Hydrology.

Participants were excited with the training and

commended the organizers for the quality of the training that involved theory and field work.

Sulaiman Abubakar (AKRISA), Fatima Mohammed Umar (Hadejia and Jama'are River Basin Development Authority), Zainab Jafar Baba (AKRISAL) and Abdulhamid Wada of Ministry of Environment both said the training was the first of its kind they attended in terms of the quality of the modules and knowledge acquired.

A female participant making her contribution

Professor Abdulganiy Shuaib of WACWISA (left) presenting a certificate to one of the participants

Dr Murtala M. Badamasi, Coordinator Training of CDA

Prof Abdulganiy Shuaib of WACWISA, Director CDA, Prof Jibrin M. Jibrin, Dr Murtala Baddamasi and other participants at a Field Work

Dr Murtala M. Badamasi providing a demonstration to the participants at the field work

Participants watching farms ravaged by flooding

A group photograph of the participants of the workshop

How CDA Alumnus Makes Impact In Kano, Jigawa And Niger Republic

... Engages more than 200 Youth, Women on Climate Change Initiative

An alumnus of the Centre for Dryland Agriculture (CDA), Abdulmajid Abubakar has been making positive impacts on socio-economic development of inhabitants of Kano, Jigawa and Maradi in Niger Republic through an initiative that aims to protect the diverse effects of climate change.

Mr Abubakar Abdulmajid has established Eyes on the Environment Initiative (EEI), a non-governmental, non-political, and non-profit-making youth-led organisation, which champions a sustainable future, in line with the Sustainable Development Goals (SDG) numbers 4, 6, 7, 10, 13 & 17.

The EEI raises awareness on the impact of Deforestation, Desertification and Drought on the most vulnerable and degraded landscapes in dryland regions of Nigeria and the Niger Republic. It nurtures the youth to love nature and be conscious of the environment at a very early age. At the same time, it educates the most vulnerable communities, women and children on mitigation and adaptation measures to build capacity and contribute to minimising its effects on people and the planet.

This EEI also encourages traditional leaders to partake in climate action, as they are very close to the grassroots and are highly respected by the people. This aids in providing

local environmental governance within affected communities.

Abdulmajid Abubakar studied MSc Natural Resource Management and Climate Change and graduated in 2017. He said the CDA had provided him with the training opportunity that was at par with international standards and served as an eye-opener for him to interact and meet with students from many African countries". Furthermore, he added that "this diversity made the experience at the centre more captivating and unique. Through my training at the CDA, I was able to unlock my full potential".

The CDA training had equipped him with the knowledge and necessary skills to venture into this initiative, especially looking at the situation every year in Nigeria, as thousands of households lose their means of livelihood due to the devastating effect of floods. Also, food production keeps declining and the government spends huge amounts of money in rehabilitating properties damaged as a result of the disasters. Also, diseases are spreading due to our actions and inactions towards the environment. Women and children are left vulnerable to social vices. "We can only address food insecurity, famine, hunger, floods, and desertification if we are ready to halt Climate Change. This is our focus in EEI," he said.

Founder/Project Coordinator of EEI, Abdulmajid Abubakar with his team inspecting seedlings to be donated to FGC Kano

The CDA alumnus said the training on Climate Change he received propelled his interest to establish the initiative with the focus of poverty alleviation and the desire to boost rural livelihood, provide better life for women and children and enhance access to clean potable water as well as sustainable agriculture and environmental development. He admitted that CDA training made him become an environmentalist and climate change activist.

The EEI has branches in Jigawa and Kano States as well as Maradi in Niger Republic, and has received several requests of northern states and beyond to extend its services to them. His plan is to expand the coverage to other states and parts of the African continent. Presently, the EEI has more than 200 active members and volunteers with special interests in Climate Action, Environmental education, Clean Energy, Restoration, Waste management and Rural livelihood. Others are Environmental sustainability, Quality of life for women and children and Equal opportunity for qualitative education for all.

In terms of achievement, the EEI engaged more than ten (10) traditional leaders to partake in climate action; trained and introduced the 17 sustainable development goals to more than 150 youth and convinced Crown Flour Mills company on the need to limit and offset their carbon footprints. The company donated and planted 15,000 indigenous tree species in some universities in northern Nigeria.

The EEI engaged youth, motor station union workers and the management of Kano Zoological Garden as volunteers in clean-up exercises and donated 250 seedlings to 250 households at Nasarawa and Dantanoma quarters in Gumel Local Government Area on 5th June 2020 to mark the World Environment Day (WED2020). They also celebrated the day with some Almajiri children in Kano State.

The EEI also planted more than 3500 seedlings in primary schools across Kano and Jigawa States and organised a community-based initiative in Gumel LGA to clear drainage systems to reduce the effect of flash floods within communities.

In commemoration of the World Youth Skills Day 2022, the initiative collaborated with Break-Free from Plastic Awareness Initiative (BFP AI) and trained 72 community women and youth in Zabi community of Zaria L.G.A. Kaduna State, on the production of biomass briquettes as a substitute for burning fossil fuel. This was strategically done to offer them employment opportunities.

As Climate change and Global Energy Crisis threaten the lives and livelihoods of billions of people worldwide, the EEI collaborated with Future Energy Leaders Nigeria and organized a Tree Planting and Sensitization Campaign on 5th July, 2022 with the theme: "Climate Action Now", at Community School Asokoro, FCT Abuja.

Abdulmajid Abubakar received the UNFCC acknowledgement letter to attend COP27 in Sharm el-Sheikh Egypt in November 2022.

According to him, CDA has modelled him to make a lot of impacts in protecting the environment.

A demonstration of Africa demands for climate justice by the EEI Founder, Abdulmajid Abubakar

The EEI has more than 200 active members and volunteers with special interests in Climate Action, Environmental education, Clean Energy, Restoration, Waste management and Rural livelihood. Others are Environmental sustainability, Quality of life for women and children and Equal opportunity for qualitative education for all

Tree planting, a project aimed at empowering girls with climate education and skills to protect the environment

CDA Team Attends 1st Symposium of the FOOD4WA Network

The Centre for Dryland Agriculture, Bayero University, Kano, one of the World Bank and AFD supported Africa Centres of Excellence (ACE) in the agriculture thematic area participated at the Symposium and workshop organized by the Food for West Africa FOOD4WA. FOOD4WA is a network of the agriculture ACEs that brings together the seven Agriculture ACEs from six African countries whose activities focus on agriculture, food security and nutrition.

The Centre Leader, Professor J.M. Jibrin, Deputy Centre Leader, Professor S.G. Mohammed, and Project Manager, Dr Yusuf Garba, represented the CDA at the symposium.

The Africa Centre of Excellence in Agriculture for Food and Nutrition Security (CEA-AGRISAN) at Cheikh Anta Diop University in Dakar, Senegal hosted the workshop.

The main thrust of the network was strengthening skills and training young Africans, who can take up the challenge of food self-sufficiency, as well as food and nutritional security. Additionally, the universities hosting the Centres will collaborate with sister universities to exchange knowledge and promote the mobility of students and faculty in Africa. CERSA from Togo, CERPP from Niger, CEFTER and CDA from Nigeria, CCBAD from Côte d'Ivoire, AGRISAN from Senegal and WACCI from Ghana were represented at the symposium.

At the end of the workshop, key activities outlined in the work-plan of the FOOD4WA were reviewed and Centres mandated to conduct / host certain activities on behalf of the network.

The CDA was given the hosting right of the first International Conference by the Network which is scheduled to take place in September 2023.

Cross section of the CDA participants during the Symposium of the FOOD4WA held from 24-25th August 2022 (The Director, CDA Prof. J.M. Jibrin at the extreme left, The Deputy Centre Leader, Prof. S.G. Mohammed at the Centre and Dr. Y. Garba (Project Manager, ACE-Impact Project) at the extreme right)

Group photograph of participants during the Symposium of the FOOD4WA held from 24-25th August 2022

Group photograph of the Centre Leaders of the seven Africa Centres of Excellence (ACE) in the agriculture thematic area comprising the FOOD4WA network. At the extreme right is the Director/Centre Leader of CDA (Prof. J.M. Jibrin)

Determination of DNA concentration using Nano drop

CDA's Cutting-Edge Research

Weighing of Minute Quantity of Sample Using Analytical Weighing Balance

Inoculation of Explants in Biosafety Cabinet

Observation of Datepalm Plantlets in Growth Room

Hardening of Datepalm Plantlets in Automated Screen House

Tissue Cultured Datepalm Plantlets in Rooting Media

SCAN HERE
for more information

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Fatima Zahra Buhari
Crops & Cropping System in the Drylands

Research Focus

The focus of the Research is on Phytic acid, Iron, and Zinc levels among approximately 1430 sorghum genotypes comprising popular cultivars, parental lines, advance breeding lines and selected germplasm accessions was to investigate the relationship between these nutrients and their availability in these genotypes. Phytic acid is a compound found in plant seeds and grains that can bind with minerals such as iron and zinc, reducing their absorption in the human body. Iron and zinc are important nutrients for human health, and a deficiency in these minerals can lead to serious health problems. The research would aim to identify sorghum genotypes with lower levels of Phytic acid, and higher levels of iron and zinc, which would make them more nutritious for human consumption. Overall, the research would contribute to the development of more nutritious sorghum genotypes that can help address micronutrient deficiencies and hidden hunger and improve the health of people who consume them.

What the research seeks to address in line with SDG's

First, it addresses SDG 2 - Zero Hunger, by seeking to develop more nutritious sorghum genotypes that can help address micronutrient deficiencies and improve the health of people who consume them. Iron and zinc deficiencies, for example, are major public health problems in many developing countries, and improving the availability of these nutrients in sorghum could contribute to reducing malnutrition and hidden hunger.

Secondly, the research aligns with SDG 3 - Good Health and Well-being, by focusing on the nutritional quality of sorghum and its potential to improve the health of people who consume it.

By reducing Phytic acid levels and increasing the bioavailability of iron and zinc, the research could contribute to improving the health of populations that rely on sorghum as a dietary staple.

Finally, the research aligns with SDG 12 - Responsible Consumption and Production, by promoting sustainable and responsible production methods that can help to reduce the environmental impact of agriculture. Developing more nutritious sorghum genotypes with lower levels of Phytic acid could lead to increased demand for these varieties, and may contribute to reducing the reliance on more resource-intensive crops. Additionally, the study of processing methods that can increase the bioavailability of iron and zinc could lead to more efficient and sustainable production methods for sorghum-based foods.

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